

Development Interventions and Conflict Dynamics: An Analysis of the World Bank–Funded
Multi-Sectoral Crisis Recovery Project in North-East Nigeria

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ABBREVIATION

MCRP- Multi-Sectoral Crisis Recovery Project.

NERP- North-East Nigeria Recovery and Peacebuilding Project.

ISR- Implementation Status Report.

DDR- Disarmament, Demobilization, and Reintegration

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This essay examines the World Bank-funded Multi-Sectoral Crisis Recovery Project (MCRP) in North-East Nigeria to assess how development interventions shape conflict dynamics. The project is selected because it clearly qualifies as a development and peacebuilding programme, combining livelihood restoration, infrastructure rehabilitation, and social cohesion across Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa States, areas severely affected by the Boko Haram insurgency. The paper is structured in four parts. First, it introduces the conflict context and outlines the MCRP's objectives. Second, the case analysis evaluates the project's impact on security, livelihoods, and social cohesion using programme evidence. Third, it applies a theoretical framework based on Galtung's positive and negative peace and the security-development nexus. Finally, a counterfactual reflection considers how the conflict might have evolved without the project. Overall, the essay argues that while the MCRP strengthened community resilience and reduced some conflict pressures, it could not on its own end armed violence.

PROJECT COMPONENT

The Northern Region of Nigeria has been experiencing an insurgency, led by the Boko Haram, since 2009, following a harsh crackdown on the group by the Nigerian military. This caused widespread displacement, destruction of infrastructure, and severely undermined social cohesion and local economies. In response to this complex humanitarian and security crisis, the World Bank launched the Multi-Sectoral Crisis Recovery Project (MCRP), also

known as the North-East Nigeria Recovery and Peacebuilding Project (NERP), particularly in Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa, to address the multidimensional impacts of conflict and displacement in North-East Nigeria.

According to (World Bank, 2017, p. 18), the project seeks to simultaneously (1) “support the Government of Nigeria towards rehabilitating and improving critical service delivery infrastructure, improve the livelihood opportunities of conflict and displacement-affected communities, and strengthen social cohesion in North East Participating States of Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa”; and (2) “in the event of an Eligible Crisis or Emergency, to provide immediate and effective response to said Eligible Crisis or Emergency, through the proposed Contingent Emergency Response Component”. Rather than acting as a single-track development programme, the project is built around four related components (World Bank, 2017, pp. 21-23), each targeting a particular dimension of post-conflict recovery and stability.

- **Component 1: Peace, Stability, and Social Cohesion**, which supports the stabilization of conflict-affected communities by providing emergency livelihood assistance, restoring income-generating capacity, promoting peacebuilding and psychosocial support initiatives, and strengthening inclusive citizen–government engagement for recovery planning.
- **Component 2: Infrastructure Rehabilitation and Service Delivery**, which focuses on addressing physical destruction and disrupted public services through the rehabilitation of transport infrastructure, restoration of municipal services,

reconstruction of schools and health facilities, and rehabilitation of key public buildings for local governance.

- **Component 3: Technical Assistance and Programme Management**, aims to strengthen government coordination and implementation capacity by supporting recovery planning and performance management, financing project management and accountability systems, building institutional capacity across government levels, and establishing citizen engagement and third-party monitoring mechanisms.
- **Component 4: Contingent Emergency Response**, allowing for the rapid reallocation of project funds in the event of a new emergency or crisis.

RESULT ANALYSIS

Security and Stability: The MCRP specifically sought to stabilize communities so that recovery and returns could begin. In practice, the initiative prioritized labor-intensive public works, targeted cash-for-work schemes, psychosocial care for trauma sufferers, and the formation/financing of local peace groups-activities designed to minimize immediate vulnerability and promote local conflict management (Malkawi, 2025). By April- May 2025, the Implementation Status Report (ISR) detailed that the project had targeted 13,500 trauma sufferers (indicator met) and had reached over 4.41 million direct beneficiaries (142% of the original objective), with 1.3 million reached through the peacebuilding/livelihoods

component and 128,943 people receiving cash-for-work (161% of the target) (Malkawi, 2025). The types of outputs prioritized in each component signify the project's ability to address major service gaps and economic needs in the BAY states. By focusing on sectors that have a direct impact on community welfare, the project ensures that these outcomes are not only technically correct but also socially relevant and responsive to urgent needs. Additionally, the project's ability to reach its goal successfully indicates its clear success in producing visible, measurable, and clearly defined outputs that are observable, thereby improving accountability and enabling more accurate tracking of progress in a highly variable operational environment. It further shows good operational planning, adaptive management, and partner coordination in a fragile setting where weak institutions frequently slow or undermine recovery attempts.

In November 2025, the project's Implementation Completion and Results Report indicated that in 2020, the MCRP had its components revised to better respond to changing demands in conflict-affected areas. The redesigned structure prioritized livelihoods and climate-smart agriculture in Component 1, improved connectivity, health, and education services while introducing cash-for-work interventions in Component 2, and reinforced regional coordination and knowledge management in Component 3. Building on these changes, a new restructuring in 2024 increased agricultural support, reduced labor-intensive public works activities under Component 1, strengthened operations and maintenance arrangements under Component 2, and expanded Component 3 to support future project studies and learning (WorldBank, 2025). These changes reflect the project's ability to adjust its design during implementation to respond to contextual and operational factors. These

revisions are significant during implementation as they increase operational flexibility, reallocate resources to activities with clearer delivery potential, and strengthen institutional arrangements required for maintaining rehabilitated assets.

Overall, the results imply a robust short-term stability and reduced acute vulnerability among beneficiaries. Rapid income support and psychosocial assistance reduce desperation that can drive local violence, while local peace groups create forums for dispute resolution. Analyzed through the security–development nexus, such stabilization operations can reduce recruitment and small-scale violence by increasing conflict opportunity costs; thus, the MCRP’s extensive coverage of Labor-Intensive Public Work and agricultural inputs is likely to result in fewer micro-level tensions. However, there are limitations. Measured decreases in violent occurrence are less directly reported in the ISR, as it is concerned with outputs. The ISR identifies residual risk (political/governance and institutional capability) and observes that some social-inclusion indicators, such as increasing women’s participation in peace groups, did not meet targets. The project’s inability to meet this target could reflect a mix of contextual, design, and operational constraints. Factors such as male-dominated local administration systems, religious and cultural norms, and continued violence affect women’s ability to fully participate in peacekeeping and security efforts, and the project design may not have taken these into account. Additionally, the project’s priorities are put on service and livelihood engagements, which are more measurable than social cohesion outcomes. Furthermore, ongoing militant activities in nearby areas like Gombe and Taraba imply that stabilization is dependent on larger security conditions, and

without matching improvements in territory-level security and protection, localized gains can be undone.

Livelihood & Economic Recovery: The livelihoods pillar is the most targeted area through which the World Bank aims to change conflict drivers. The ISR demonstrates significant progress in this sector, with more than 1.3 million beneficiaries receiving enhanced livelihood possibilities, 44,448 farmers adopting climate-smart techniques (160% of the objective), 42 small-scale irrigation schemes repaired, and cash-for-work beneficiaries substantially exceeding targets. These interventions align with grievances (Pizzolo, 2020) and opportunity-cost theories (Fauerbach, 2018); by restoring productive assets (seeds, tools, irrigation) and providing temporary income, the project diminishes material incentives for recruitment into armed organizations while giving alternatives to criminal livelihoods. However, the sustainability and inclusiveness of these outcomes are unclear. The ISR emphasizes its high numerical reach but does not provide independent impact evaluations demonstrating long-term revenue increases or changing recruiting trends. There is concern about whether these benefits went to the most vulnerable groups, especially young men who are susceptible to recruitment or primarily to more accessible households. Additionally, many of its interventions, like cash-for-work, are fundamentally short-term, and without sustained market linkages, livelihoods may stop once project funding ceases, undercutting long-term conflict reduction efforts. These reflect a criticism of short-term stabilization programs within the security-development nexus: immediate relief is necessary but insufficient for structural transformation.

Social Cohesion & Institutional Strengthening. MCRP invested in social cohesion through local peace groups, community dialogue, psychosocial assistance, and citizen-government engagement, and invested substantially in restoring service delivery under Components 1 and 2. According to the ISR, over 3.1 million individuals currently have access to services and infrastructure (128% of the initial infrastructure target), and there has been progress on capacity building and multi-state coordination frameworks. These restored services will contribute to the reestablishment of state legitimacy and intercommunal normalcy, both of which are pathways to positive peace (institutional trust) and reduced violence. Nonetheless, implementation risks limit the translation of infrastructure into long-term social cohesion. The ISR's risk register classifies political and institutional capacity as moderate to high at various levels, while acknowledging inadequate progress on some social inclusion metrics (for example, women's participation targets). Factors like donor dependency and disaster capitalism – where elites and big businesses benefit from reconstruction contracts- may hinder the extent to which the project's primary objective is achieved. However, while the MCRP's investments are well aligned with the security-development nexus theory, empirical attribution to long-term peace remains uncertain. Overall, the MCRP exhibits the classic security–development nexus pattern; however, the project's long-term impact on negative peace is determined by the durability of economic gains, the depth of institutional reforms, and broader security developments outside the scope of the project. In Yobe, Borno, and Adamawa, these interventions have aided in facilitating the partial return of displaced people and alleviated communal tensions by enhancing access to jobs, schools, health facilities, and basic amenities. The ISR's strong

output metrics are encouraging, but they do not eliminate the drivers of ongoing violence nor demonstrate long-term transformation of conflict causes. Ongoing armed attack and the continuous presence of militant groups reflect that negative peace remains fragile in these states. Finally, the MCRP may reflect how development-driven stability initiatives might impact post-conflict situations, while also showing its limitations in areas where armed conflict persists.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

In his concept of peace, Galtung makes a distinction between negative peace, which is understood as the absence of direct violence or armed conflict (Galtung, 1969), and positive peace, as the absence of structural violence. This means existing functional institutions, equitable access to resources, the presence of social justice, and harmonious social relations (Grewal, 2024). In the context of North-East Nigeria, neither form of peace seems to be fully present. While reduced armed conflict may indicate a period of negative peace, recurring insurgent attacks, communal violence, and widespread displacement show that even the absence of violence remains fragile. More importantly, the deep structural conditions that contribute to the absence of positive peace- poverty, unemployment, inequality continue to persist. These systemic inequalities not only perpetuate human misery but also feed the frustrations that drive recruitment into armed groups like Boko Haram. According to (Galtung, 1969), military measures alone cannot bring peace to North-East Nigeria; instead, peace requires purposeful developmental interventions addressing

issues related to livelihoods, service delivery, social cohesion, and state-society interactions. Development-oriented peacebuilding projects, such as MCRP, are critical in bridging the gap between negative and positive peace, as they seek to transform the social and economic conditions that enable violence in the first place, rather than simply suppressing it.

The security-development nexus posits that security and development are inextricably linked: security enables development, while development reduces the drivers of insecurity. The World Bank and major policy actors framed this clearly in the World Development Report 2011: that fragile and conflict-affected states need integrated approaches where security, justice, and development policies are coordinated rather than isolated. This research emphasizes that poverty, inequality, youth unemployment, and weak institutions increase the likelihood of violence, and that long-term peace involves both protection (security) and structural transformation (WorldBank, 2011). This forms the operational logic behind projects like MCRP: rebuild services and restore livelihoods. When combined, they disrupt the loop that supports insurgency recruitment and local violence.

Analyzing this project, while it focuses on demand-side factors (livelihood and social cohesion), input distributions (seed for farmers), and financing social cohesion initiatives, it may provide quick relief but not long-term employment or market integration. Hence, there is a danger of relapse once the project support ends. Furthermore, if aid is regarded as biased, particularly in favor of specific genders (the percentage of which are women) and communities, it may exacerbate tensions, emphasizing the importance of local consultation and communal sensitivities, particularly in conflict-affected areas. Building on beneficial

experiences and lessons learned from similar emergency crises, and ensuring alignment with local priorities, particularly those of the Nigerian government, are essential for conditions to achieve positive peace. Lastly, while the emergency crisis responses are essential for short-term relief, they often fail to address the structural roots of violence.

REFLECTION

The World Bank recognizes conflict as a multifaceted deficit, which is reflected in the MCRP. In this project, violence is acknowledged not only as a result of economic hardship but also as a political and security issue rooted in government failures, power, and armed group dynamics, as reflected in Component 3 of the project design. The absence of the MCRP and similar projects in these regions would result in more destabilization and increment of gap between military stabilization and civilian recovery. The destruction of basic infrastructure by militant groups strips communities of economic survival mechanisms and social institutions. Without these recovery efforts, these deprivations would exacerbate structural violence, which is the root of long-term conflict.

While military operations have degraded Boko Haram territorially, security gains are unlikely to be sustained without corresponding improvements in governance, service delivery, and livelihoods. At a local level, communities would see the state primarily through a repressive security lens, rather than as a source of welfare and protection. This destroys governmental legitimacy, a key motivator of insurgency, and perpetuates the region's violent political economy. Even with initiatives such as the MCRP, such alone would not end armed conflict

in areas where violent actors continue to operate. This underscores a key paradox in the conflict-development relationship: development interventions can reduce vulnerability and control conflict pressures, but they cannot replace effective security containment. The MCRP boosted livelihood access, social services, and infrastructure, but ongoing violence in sections of Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe shows that development gains do not always translate into negative peace.

Reflecting on the project, it is quite unclear if it was developed with a good grasp of the key drivers of recruitment and armed conflict in the BAY states. Rather than displaying a clear diagnosis of these forces, the project looks to approach the issue with a predetermined set of development options. While such initiatives may help with short-term stabilization, they may not necessarily address the underlying causes of armed mobilization. As a result, while the project is characterized as transformative, its design suggests it is better suited to producing short-term stability than to long-term conflict transformation, especially when the fundamental drivers of violence are not clearly integrated into project aims.

Additionally, if this project had been constructed differently, such as with more direct reintegration paths for at-risk youth and former combatants, the influence on conflict dynamics could have been more transformative. While the MCRP addressed livelihoods broadly, its engagement with ex-combatants and high-risk youth appears to be restricted and undisclosed, resulting in a disconnect between recovery programming and hard security stabilization. A more explicit Disarmament, Demobilization, and Reintegration (DDR)-linked design could have had a more direct impact on recruitment pipelines. While the World Bank does not engage directly in DDR, particularly in FCV contexts where security-sector

interventions fall outside its mandate, the *reintegration* component of DDR overlaps significantly with development-oriented programming. Reintegration, understood as social and economic inclusion rather than disarmament, aligns closely with development objectives and could have strengthened the programme's conflict-mitigating impact. By avoiding more targeted reintegration approaches, the project may have missed an opportunity to address recruitment dynamics more directly, indicating a preference for indirect conflict reduction through development over direct involvement with ex-combatants. This reflects a broader development-first approach, which may lower vulnerability to recruitment but is less successful in combating ongoing armed mobilization.

Overall, this demonstrates that development and conflict are mutually reinforcing. In unstable situations like North-East Nigeria, underdevelopment fosters violence, which ruins development gains. The MCRP demonstrates how development interventions can reduce violence by stabilizing communities, restoring dignity through work, and reestablishing trust between citizens and the state. However, it also demonstrates that without matching advances in security governance and political stability, growth will only reduce, not eradicate, violent conflict. The relationship between conflict and development is thus not linear, but rather highly interdependent: peace requires development to exist, and development needs security to survive.

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